

E-Learning to go

Module 2 - Unit 10 Media Selection in eLearning

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Media for Teaching and Learning

- There is a very wide range of media available for teaching and learning. In particular:
 - text, audio, video, computing, social media and emerging technologies all have unique characteristics that make them useful for teaching and learning;
 - the choice or combination of media will need to be determined by:
 - the overall teaching philosophy behind the teaching;
 - the presentational and structural requirements of the subject matter or content;
 - the skills that need to be developed in learners;
 - and not least by the imagination of the teacher or instructor (and increasingly learners themselves) in identifying possible roles for different media;
 - courses can be structured around individual students' interests, allowing them to seek appropriate content and resources
 - content is now increasingly open and freely available over the Internet; as a result learners can seek, use and apply information beyond the bounds of what a professor or teacher may dictate;
 - students can create their own online personal learning environments;
 - many students will still need a structured approach that guides their learning;
 - teacher presence and guidance is likely to be necessary to ensure high quality learning
 - teachers need to find the middle ground between complete learner freedom and over-direction to enable learners to develop the key skills needed in a digital age.

Models for Media Selection

- Given the importance of the topic, there is **relatively little literature** on how to choose appropriate media or technologies for teaching.
- A review of more recent publications on media selection suggests that despite the rapid developments in media and technology over the last 20 years,
 - the ACTIONS model (Bates, 1995) is one of the major models still being applied, although with further amendments and additions (see for instance, Baytak, undated; Lambert and Williams, 1999; Koumi, 2006).
 - Indeed the modified the ACTIONS model, which was developed for **distance education to the SECTIONS model** (from ACTIONS to SECTIONS) to cover the use of media in campus-based as well as distance education (Bates and Poole, 2003).
 - Koumi (2006) and Mayer (2009) have come closest to developing models of media selection.
 - **Mayer has developed twelve principles of multimedia design** based on extensive research, resulting in what Mayer calls a cognitive theory of multimedia learning.
- **Mayer's approach is valuable at a more micro-level** when it comes to designing specific multimedia educational materials, as is Koumi's work.
- **At the same time, every teacher, instructor, and increasingly learner, needs to make decisions in this area, often on a daily basis and therefore a model for selection is needed!**

Models for Media Selection: Characteristics

- A model for technology selection and application is needed that has the following characteristics:
 - it will work in a wide variety of learning contexts;
 - it allows decisions to be taken at both a strategic, institution-wide level, and at a tactical, instructional, level;
 - it gives equal attention to educational and operational issues;
 - it will identify critical differences between different media and technologies, thus enabling an appropriate mix to be chosen for any given context;
 - it is easily understood, pragmatic and cost-effective;
 - it will accommodate new developments in technology.
- The SECTIONS model is based on research, has stood the test of time, and has been found to be practical.

....SECTIONS stands for...

SECTIONS Model for Media Selection by Bates

➤ Further Reading SECTIONS Model: <https://opentextbc.ca/teachinginadigitalage/chapter/9-1-models-for-media-selection/>

SECTIONS Model: YouTube Introduction Video

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cwmo2NLBbkU&t=394s>

Takeaways SECTION MODEL

1. Selecting media and technologies is a complex process, involving a very wide range of interacting variables.
2. There is currently **no generally accepted** theory or process for media selection. The SECTIONS model however provides a set of criteria or questions the result of which can help inform an instructor when making decisions about which media or technologies to use.
3. Because of the wide range of factors influencing media selection and use, an inductive or intuitive approach to decision-making, informed by a careful analysis of all the criteria in the SECTIONS framework, is one practical way to approach decision-making about media and technologies for teaching and learning.
4. However, media selection needs to be integrated within the broader framework of course design.

- How does this help us if we want to realize a course?
- My personal target at the beginning was not to do something perfect, which is based on latest research results.
- My target was to survive and to be fast!
- Therefore my approach was to convert existing lecture documents in E-Learning content.
- And exactly this is my recommendation to you!

E-Learning to go!

E-learning should enable flexible independent learning, independent of location and time!

Then creating e-learning must be as easy as creating PowerPoint presentations - And it already is!

Reuse & change flexibility

Use of already existing PPT documents with high flexibility for changes

Authentic

Authentic e-learning training with self-produced explanatory videos & screen recordings

Media & Learner Activation

Integration of various media such as YouTube videos and tests or quizzes to activate learners

Autonomy & costs

Autonomous creation and maintenance of learning packages in the office with cost-effective technical solutions and independent of third parties (e.g. video studios or e-learning agencies)

Dare to work in loops!

Preparation Questions for Unit 10 (Homework - workload target 60 minutes)

Prepare yourself for our lecture by analyzing and summarizing the boundary conditions for e-exams and e-feedback at your home university

1. Clark & Mayer (2016) suggest that there are six possible functions of graphics. Please investigate based on literature which those are!
 - Based on these categories, it is recommended that decorative and representational images are minimised, and instead focus on graphics that help the learner to understand the material presented, or organise the material in a useful way.
2. Please analyze 2 of your own lectures (1xgeneral topic e.g. lecture introduction + 1xcomplex topic) and create 2 cake diagrams which show the quantity of questions of the 6 types in % and/or absolute values.
3. Please add the topic of the chosen lectures + one sentence regarding the content + the diagram on 2 PPT slides. If time allows you will be invited to present the result of your analysis.

Clark & Mayer (2016) suggest that there are six possible functions of graphics:

it's your turn!

Graphic type	Description
Decorative	Visuals added for aesthetic appeal or humor
Representational	Visuals that illustrate the appearance of an object
Organizational	Visuals that show qualitative relationships among content
Relational	Visuals that summarize quantitative relationships
Transformational	Visuals that illustrate changes in time or over space
Interpretive	Visuals that make intangible phenomena visible and concrete

How to use Mayer's 12 Principles of Multimedia

What we are talking about is multimedia learning!

- Multimedia learning can be defined as a form of computer-aided instruction that uses two modalities concurrently.
- This means learning through the combined use of visuals (through pictures, animations, text, and videos) and audio (through narrated voiceover).
- If you're creating a training video, PowerPoint presentation, or eLearning course, how do you ensure your final product will be an effective learning resource?
- To help us create the most effective multimedia learning experiences, Richard Mayer has developed a theory of 12 Principles of Multimedia Learning.
- Think of these principles as 'guidelines' as you develop your digital learning experiences – learning videos, eLearning courses, and instructor-led PowerPoint presentations.
- As you begin building your next multimedia learning experience, it may make sense to print out the 12 principles as a checklist.
- Keep the checklist next to your computer as a helpful reference to design and develop your learning experience

1. The Coherence Principle

- First up is the Coherence Principle, which states that **humans learn best when extraneous, distracting material is not included.**
- Simply said, cut out the extras. Use only the information that the learner needs. And most often, that means simple text and simple visuals that relate directly to the learning topic. Remove all the fluff.

COHERENCE PRINCIPLE

This

Not This

Cut out the extras. Remove all the fluff. Use only the information that the learner needs. That means simple text and simple visuals that relate directly to the learning topic.

How to use the Coherence Principle:

- You can use the Coherence Principle as you're planning your visual elements. Ask yourself, "Is this image 100% necessary to help with comprehension? Or could you find a better one? Does this message use simple enough language so the audience will understand? Maybe I could trim down a few words."
- The Coherence Principle is also quite helpful when you're editing your training video or eLearning course. As you re-watch the experience, make sure to watch with a critical "Coherence Principle" eye. Determine how you can reduce, simplify, and clarify.

Ways to apply the coherence principle

REMOVE EXTRANEIOUS WORDS

- Cute stories and interesting pieces of trivia can feel to the instructional designer like harmless additions to a multimedia presentation, but research suggests that they may not produce the desired effects. The rationale for excluding extraneous words is based upon the cognitive theory that assumes that working memory capacity is very limited.
- Clark & Mayer (2016, p155) identify three distinct types of extraneous wording used for different purposes:
 - for **interest**: related to the topic but not relevant to the instructional goal
 - for **elaboration**: expands upon the key ideas of the lesson
 - to **technical details** that go beyond the key ideas of the lesson
- They recommend against all three, suggesting that when these additions are more interesting than the fundamental content of a lesson that they can distract learners away from achieving the instructional goals. Not only do they not help learning, but in some cases they can even hurt learning.
- Evidence for this can be found in many studies conducted over the last 20 years. Mayer, Heiser and Lonn (2001) conducted an experiment that concluded that **presenting more information can result in less learning**: the addition of additional narration segments to the lesson distracted students away from the core instructional goals. A related study conducted in 2007 found that college students who read the lesson *with* seductive details “spent less time reading the relevant text, recalled less of the relevant text and showed shallower processing on an essay task as compared to students who read the lightning passage without seductive details” (Clark & Mayer, 2016. p156).
- Adding seductive details harms learning by **distracting learners** from the important information and by **disrupting the coherence** of the lesson.

2. The Signaling Principle

- Next up is the Signaling Principle, which essentially means that **humans learn best when they are shown exactly what to pay attention to on the screen**. If there is a ton of information on the screen, how is the learner supposed to know what is the most important part?

SIGNALING PRINCIPLE

The diagram shows two side-by-side examples of text presentation. Both examples feature the same text: "The methodical and deliberate activity of creating and continuously improving maintenance systems." Below the text are several interlocking gears. In the left example, the word "methodical" is highlighted in a green box, and a green arrow points to it. Below this example is a green box with the word "This". In the right example, the text is plain, and below it is a grey box with the words "Not This".

Show the learner exactly what to pay attention to on the screen.
Highlight important words and use arrows to point out significant information.

Example highlighter & Camtasia Callouts

How to use the Signaling Principle:

- As a learning developer, this is where you can utilize the signaling principle by thoughtfully using features such as highlighting important words and using animated arrows to point out significant information. Another way you can use the signaling principle is by having slides or scenes that separate learning sections. This is a quick and easy way to signal to the learner that we're moving on to the next topic.

3. The Redundancy Principle

- Next up? The Redundancy Principle. This principle suggests that **humans learn best with narration and graphics, as opposed to narration, graphics, and text**. The theory here is that if you already have narration and graphics, then the text on top is just redundant information. And this can be overwhelming for a learner.

REDUNDANCY PRINCIPLE

This

Not This

With an audio narration voiceover, use only graphics on screen. Don't use graphics and text. Add optional closed captioning for learners that prefer to read subtitles.

Example: Handout E-learning Course

How to use the Redundancy Principle:

- You can use this principle for videos or eLearning courses that have narrated audio. Try to only include graphics or text, but not both together. Or if they are together, make the text minimal.
- Many people prefer reading text on screen so what is helpful is to include closed captioning that can be optionally turned on and off. This can't be done in all cases, but whenever possible it does help.

4. The Spatial Contiguity Principle

- The Spatial Contiguity Principle is about the actual space in between your text and visuals on the screen, stating that **humans learn best when relevant text and visuals are physically close together.**

SPATIAL CONTIGUITY PRINCIPLE

This

Not This

Keep all related text and graphics physically close together in your frame.
Make it easy for learners to understand how text and graphics are related.

In the example above, the bones of the skull are labelled using a legend, with descriptions off to the side of the image. Numbers are used to link the areas identified with the names. This divides learners' attention and should be avoided.

In this example, labels are provided on top of the graphic, which makes it easier to focus on the content.

How to use the Spatial Contiguity Principle:

- This one makes sense intuitively. You should keep all related text and graphics physically close together in your frame. This makes it much easier for learners to process the information, using less energy to decipher meaning. This principle is pretty straight forward. Make it easy for your audience to know where to look for information.

Live E-Learning Course Example!

5. The Temporal Contiguity Principle

- The Temporal Contiguity Principle states that **humans learn best when corresponding words and visuals are presented together, instead of in consecutive order.**

TEMPORAL CONTIGUITY PRINCIPLE

This **Not This**

Make sure the visuals and audio *occur at the same time* as opposed to having the voiceover audio play before the visual is shown.

Live E-Learning Course Example!

How to use the Temporal Contiguity Principle:

- If you're introducing a new process, the animation (or visual) should be occurring at the same time as the voiceover audio. This is preferred to having the voiceover audio play first, and then watching a visual after. You can use this by making sure your voiceover audio is always timed well with your visuals or animations.

6. The Segmenting Principle

- Next is the Segmenting Principle which states that **humans learn best when information is presented in segments, rather than one long continuous stream**. Mayer found that when learners can control the pace of their learning, they performed better on recall tests.

SEGMENTING PRINCIPLE

This

Not This

Provide learners with control over their learning by including 'next' buttons and customizable video settings. Also, make sure learning is segmented into small chunks.

Live E-Learning Course Example!

How to use the Segmenting Principle:

- You can use this principle by providing learners with more control over their learning. This is done by adding next buttons or allowing the speed which a video plays.
- This principle also suggests that learning is broken up into smaller, bite-sized chunks. Make sure that no one lesson, slide, or video has too much information packed in it.

7. The Pre-Training Principle

- The Pre-training Principle states that **humans learn more efficiently if they already know some of the basics**. This often means understanding basic definitions, terms, or concepts before beginning the learning experience.
- And this makes intuitive sense. If a learner starts an eLearning course knowing about the topic, they can easily become overwhelmed once complex visuals and definitions start being thrown their way. A bit of pre-training before starting the course really would have helped.

PRE-TRAINING PRINCIPLE

This **Not This**

Instead of having learners begin the course right away, create an introductory guide that teaches the basic definitions, terms, and concepts.

Live E-Learning Course Example!

How to use the Pre-Training Principle:

- You can use this principle by creating an introductory “guide” or “cheat sheet” for learners to use throughout the course. Or you can create an entire lesson up front dedicated to understanding the basics, before the learner moves into the actual course.

8. The Modality Principle

- The Modality Principle states that **humans learn best from visuals and spoken words than from visuals and printed words**. This doesn't mean that you should never use text on screen, it simply means that if there are visuals and too much text, learners will be overwhelmed.

MODALITY PRINCIPLE

This

Not This

The rigorous, step-by-step development of total capability in Dynamic Maintenance is the key difference compared to other supply chain methodologies.

Foundational elements must be well established before developing higher-level tools and systems.

In voiceover supported learning, try to limit the amount of text used.
Rely on visuals instead. Text should be used only for key definitions, lists, and directions.

How to use the Modality Principle:

- Try to limit the amount of text you use on screen overall. Rely more on visuals, unless you need to define key terms, list steps, or provide directions.

9. The Multimedia Principle

- The Multimedia Principle states that **humans learn best from words and pictures than just words alone**. This principle is sort of the foundation of all Mayer's principles, that images and words are more effective than words alone.

MULTIMEDIA PRINCIPLE

Phase 1
Develop optimal equipment conditions

This

Phase 1 is achieved through proper implementation of our tools and systems using the Breakdown Removal Phases and the five Program Activation Steps that we will discuss further in this course.

The rigorous, step-by-step development of total capability in Dynamic Maintenance is the key difference compared to other supply chain methodologies.

Foundational elements must be well established before developing higher-level tools and systems.

Not This

Avoid using text on screen alone. Use relevant visuals instead. Be thoughtful about the visuals you select, making sure they enhance or clarify the information.

Live E-Learning Course Example!

How to use the Multimedia Principle:

- You can use this principle by being very thoughtful about the images you select. Remember that these images need to enhance or clarify the information.

10. The Personalization Principle

- The Personalization Principle says that **humans learn best from a more informal, conversational voice than an overly formal voice**. Having a more casual voice actually improves the learning experience.

PERSONALIZATION PRINCIPLE

How is Phase 1 achieved?
Phase 1 is achieved by establishing a 30% decrease in breakdowns.

This

How is Phase 1 achieved?
Phase 1 is achieved by implementing the appropriate maintenance tools and structural conformities which meet our organizations core competencies of establishing a 30% decrease in breakdowns.

Not This

Keep your message simple and casual. It allows learners feel more comfortable.
Avoid using overly professional sounding text, or long, complex words.

Live E-Learning Course Example!

How to use the Personalization Principle:

- You can use this by keeping your language simple and casual. Try to avoid overly professional sounding text, or long, complex words. It also helps to use the first person (you, I, we, our). This is where it helps to consider your audience demographics and try to match the tone of your voiceover to enhance personalization.
- Handwriting instead of computer fonts

11. The Voice Principle

- The Voice Principle states that humans learn best from a human voice than a computer voice. While Siri and Alexa are getting pretty close, there is no substitution for a human voice. It's important to note that the studies are still rather preliminary for the Voice Principle. But even so, it makes sense to use a human for your voiceover.

VOICE PRINCIPLE

This **Not This**

Use audio that was recorded professionally by a human.
Don't use an automated, robotic, computer voice.

Live E-Learning Course Example!

- **How to use the Voice Principle:**
- You can use this principle by recording your own professional narration, or hiring a professional to create an audio voiceover. Make sure your audio is high quality by using a professional microphone and mastering in audio editing software.

12. The Image Principle

- The Image Principle states that humans do not necessarily learn better from a talking head video. Talking head videos are incredibly common in eLearning courses and MOOCs. The research on this one is also still in its early phases, so take this principle with a grain of salt.
- The thinking here is that if there is important information to be learned, relevant visuals on the screen will be more effective than showing a talking head of an instructor.

IMAGE PRINCIPLE

The image shows two side-by-side video frames. The left frame is an animation of a worker in a blue uniform and yellow hard hat working on a factory floor. The right frame is a talking head video of a man in a black shirt, identified as Andrew DeBell, a Learning Consultant. Below the left frame is a green box with the word 'This' and below the right frame is a grey box with the words 'Not This'.

This **Not This**

Use relevant animations and visuals that help reinforce the audio voiceover.
Try to limit the amount of talking head screen time by the instructor.

Live E-Learning Course Example!

How to use the Image Principle:

- Instead of having a talking head of the instructor, use relevant animations and visuals that help reinforce the audio voiceover. Note that talking heads can provide some value for the instructor by building credibility and trust. This is especially useful to establish at the beginning of your learning experience. Just try to limit your use of talking heads as your video or course dives deeper into the learning content.

Images, Images, Images...but how should they look like?

- The multimedia principle, as set out by Richard Mayer in 2001, recommends that e-learning courses include words and graphics, as opposed to just words.
... or **people learn better from words and pictures than from words alone.**
- In any kind of training, it is customary to use words, either printed or spoken, as the main method of sharing information.
- Words are quick and cheap – an instructional designer doesn't need specialist software or expertise to produce them.
- Research results suggest that words and graphics are more effective when combined than just words alone, with some provisos:
 - graphics should not be an afterthought: they should be planned alongside the text to maximise understanding
 - decorative graphics do not improve learning
 - By contrast, providing words alone may encourage learners – especially those with less expertise – to engage in **shallow** learning by not making connections with other knowledge.

Six possible Functions of graphics

Clark & Mayer (2016) suggest that there are six possible functions of graphics:

Graphic type	Description
Decorative	Visuals added for aesthetic appeal or humor
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Transformational	Visuals that illustrate changes in time or over space
Interpretive	Visuals that make intangible phenomena visible and concrete

Based on these categories, it is recommended that **decorative** and **representational** images are minimised, and instead focus on graphics that help the learner to understand the material presented, or organise the material in a useful way.

Examples on the upcoming slides

Six possible functions of graphics: Examples 1-3

The Cretaceous Period

From Dinosource, for all things dinosaur.

The **Cretaceous** is a geologic period and system that spans 79 million years from the end of the **Jurassic** Period 145 million years ago (mya) to the beginning of the **Paleogene** Period 66 mya. It is the last period of the Mesozoic Era. The Cretaceous Period is usually abbreviated K, for its German translation Kreide (chalk).

The Cretaceous was a period with a relatively warm climate, resulting in high eustatic sea levels that created numerous shallow inland seas. These oceans and seas were populated with now-extinct marine **reptiles**, **ammonites** and **rudists**, while dinosaurs continued to dominate on land. During this time, new groups of mammals and birds, as well as flowering plants, appeared.

Tyrannosaurus Rex

Decorative 1 of 6

Getting started with your GoPro Hero 4

By John Savage for ShutterShack.

From the moment you take your new camera out of the box, you are ready to start filming high definition video. To use it well, though, it's important to have a basic understanding of how it works.

While GoPros are designed to be usable, there are some fundamental pointers that are useful to know before you get started.

1. Be careful removing it from the packaging
2. Set the correct date and time before you start filming
3. Download the apps on your smartphone to edit on the fly
4. Don't forget to charge your battery

The GoPro Hero 4

Representational 2 of 6

Lesson 4: Types of Backup

	Full Backup	Differential Backup	Incremental backup
What is it	A backup of all files in a specified backup set or job	A backup of all changed and new files since the last full backup	A backup of all changed and new files since the last backup of any kind
Backup speed	Slowest	Faster	Fastest
Restore speed	Fastest	Fast	Slowest
Storage needed	Most	More	Least
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Fastest restore ✓ Only needs the last full backup set to restore 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Faster & simpler restores than incremental backup ✓ Only needs he first full backup and most recent differential backup to restore 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Faster backups ✓ Less storage space used ✓ No duplicate files
Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Needs the most storage space ✗ Inefficient storage with lots of duplicates stored 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Slower backups ✗ Still stores a lot of duplicate files 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✗ Slowest restores ✗ Needs all backup sets: full & all increments to restore

Organizational 3 of 6

Graphic type	Description
Decorative	Visuals added for aesthetic appeal or humor
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Six possible functions of graphics: Examples 4-6

2016 US Senate election

2016 US Senate elections

Elections to the United States Senate were held on November 8, 2016. The presidential election, House elections, 14 gubernatorial elections, and many state and local elections were held on the same date.

In the 2016 Senate election, 34 of the 100 seats—all class 3 Senate seats—were contested in regular elections; the winners will serve six-year terms until January 3, 2023. Class 3 was last up for election in 2010, when Republicans won a net gain of six seats.

2016 US Senate election map

Relational 4 of 6

The Water Cycle

The Water Cycle

The water cycle describes the existence and movement of water on, in, and above the Earth. Earth's water is always in movement and is always changing states, from liquid to vapor to ice and back again. The water cycle has been working for billions of years and all life on Earth depends on it continuing to work. The major stages are:

1. Storage in oceans
2. Evaporation & transpiration
3. Condensation
4. Precipitation
5. Storage in ice and snow

Transformational 5 of 6

Blood Flow of the Human...

Blood Flow of the Human Heart

Interpretive 6 of 6

Graphic type	Description
Decorative	Visuals added for aesthetic appeal or humor
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The role of animations

ANIMATIONS

- A number of studies have failed to find that animations are more effective than a series of static frames depicting the same material.
- In summing up a study that compared an animation of how lightning storms develop with a series of static illustrations supported by printed text, Clark & Mayer explain this as follows:

“Presumably, the so-called passive medium of illustrations and text actually allowed for active processing because the learners had to mentally animate the changes from one frame to the next, and learners were able to control the order and pace of their processing. In contrast, the so-called active medium of animations and narration may foster passive learning because the learner did not have to mentally animate and could not control the pace and order of the presentation.”

– Clark & Mayer, 2016. pp81-3.

WHEN TO USE ANIMATIONS

- Despite the results above, animations or videos have been shown to work well in tasks that show complicated manual skills.
- They worked well in a task where students made paper flowers and learned to tie knots, for example.
- In contrast to these examples, explanations of **how complex systems work** (such as braking systems, or waves in the ocean) have been shown to be just as effective or more effective when presented as static diagrams and text rather than animations.
- They can also be useful in time-lapse sense, showing phenomena that are otherwise difficult to visualise, such as seed germination or hummingbirds in flight.
- It seems that hands-on procedures can be guided effectively using animated visuals, but conceptual information is more effectively shared with static visuals.

Which graphic types do fit to what? (1/2)

Content Type	Content Type	Useful Graphic Types*	Graphic Examples
Facts	Unique and isolated information such as specific application screens, forms, or product data	Representational, Organizational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A screen capture A table of parts' names and specifications
Concepts	Categories of objects, events, or symbols designated by a single name	Representational, Organizational, Interpretive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A tree diagram of biological species Three Excel formulas to illustrate formatting rules
Process	A description of how something works	Transformational, Interpretive, Relational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Animations of how the heart pumps blood Still diagrams to illustrate how a bicycle pump works An animation showing how a virus invades a cell

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Which graphic types do fit to what? (2/2)

Content Type	Content Type	Useful Graphic Types*	Graphic Examples
Procedure	A series of steps resulting in completion of a task	Transformational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An animated illustration of how to use a spreadsheet A diagram with arrows showing how to install a printer cable
Principle	Guidelines that result in completion of a task; cause-and-effect relationships	Transformational, Interpretive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A video showing two effective sales approaches An animation showing genes passing from parents to offspring

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Please consider when applying the multimedia principle!

There are some important considerations to the multimedia principle.

○ LEARNERS AREN'T ALWAYS THE BEST JUDGE

- While it is clear from the description above that not all graphics are equally effective, students frequently misjudge the value of these graphics.
- In a 2012 study, students did not learn better when added illustrations were purely decorative or seductive, **though they reported liking the lesson better when it contained any kind of illustration.**

Liking != learning

- As a result of this inability to distinguish helpful and unhelpful illustrations, instructional designers should only use highly relevant, instructional illustrations, and even include pointers in the text as to what to look for in the provided illustrations.

THERE IS A DIFFERENCE WITH EXPERIENCED LEARNERS

- A combination of words and graphics are particularly useful and important for novices, though less useful for expert learners.
- **Experts** are able to create their own mental images as they read a text, making use of relevant schema that they have formed previously in order to comprehend. The provision of words and graphics can actually negatively affect expert learners.
- If teaching a more advanced group of **learners who are experienced** in the topic being presented, they may be able to learn well mainly (or entirely) from text, or mainly from graphics.

STARTING WITH E-LEARNING YOU CANNOT DO EVERYTHING IN THE FIRST STEP!!!!

- Start with the pictures and text you do have and convert this to “bad” E-Learning and then work constantly on optimization!

My Process

This works already as E-Learning – you will not win an E-Learning contest but the online sessions will release you from In-Class sessions and this time can be used for upcoming optimizations!

Examples simple Corona Courses!

www.e-learningtogo.de

How to make eLearning effective?...or how and where to optimize?

- Getting learners engaged online can be a real struggle.
- Without the face-to-face interactions of instructors and classmates, online learning programs often lack a natural social component of the human learning experience. This isolation often limits learner engagement which, in turn, can lead to lower completion rates, lower enjoyment levels, and overall lower comprehension of the material.
- While modern learning technologists have yet to uncover a social equivalent, we can still use an array of available tools and strategies to boost online learner engagement.
- Why is learner engagement important?
 - Learner engagement is more than just the trendy bells and whistles you see on your LinkedIn feed. It's about tapping into human emotion. It's about keeping learners motivated. It's about encouraging the entire process of learning, from start to finish.
 - Research continues to support the connection between high student engagement and information retention, highlighting the positive effect on cognitive development and future outlook on personal learning.
- And it makes sense.
 - While the growth of online learning increases accessibility for point-of-need learning, it also adds new challenges of ensuring learner engagement and information retention.
- Our job as instructional designers and eLearning developers is to design creative, innovative ways to engage learners in an ever-changing online setting.
- Here are a few ideas to get you started:

1. Create high-quality videos

- In our digitized world, using **video in your eLearning program is a must.**
- Videos appeal to both visual and auditory senses, creating an engaging learning experience that few other eLearning mediums can provide.
- But not all video equates to 'engaging.' **Extensive time and effort must go into creating meaningful learning videos that people want to watch.**
- Literatures says they must be well-scripted, beautifully designed, and generally entertaining for your specific end-user audience. If you're creating your own videos, make sure you plan accordingly and check out our tips for [creating your own eLearning videos.](#)

I (Jochen Krieger) would say:

- **They should be authentic rather than perfect. It should be YOU as teacher, your style of teaching, your handwriting, your voice, your face to be shown in the Videos. From my perspective it is secondary that they are beautifully designed etc. as this is my personal experience**
- Taking learning video a step further, some programs allow for **interactive elements to be embedded directly into your video.** Rather than passively viewing a video, learners can interact with the screen, answering quiz questions or providing comments and feedback. This type of interactivity maximizes engagement and allows for a deeper learning experience. To try this feature in your next eLearning program, check out software such as PlayPosit or Wirewax.

Live E-Learning Course Example!

2. Design compelling visuals

- While content is always the top priority in any learning program, design still matters. A lot.
- If your eLearning program feels old and outdated, it's a sure sign that your audience will instantly disengage. Toss on your 'creativity hat' and aim to create modern, engaging visuals in the form of clean charts, graphics, illustrations, and videos.
- Captivating visuals also help guide your audience through the user experience. After all, the most impactful Powerpoint presentations contain mostly images with very little text. Depending on your learning objectives and scope of project, aim for using images/audio about 60%-80% of the time. Use text only as a supplementary tool to reinforce the learning material.
- If you aren't experienced in visual design, try sharpening your graphic design skills. Or hire a graphic designer to help create a beautifully branded eLearning experience.

**...as pointed out before my view differs slightly from theory:
Authenticity before perfectionism!**

3. Record an excellent voice over

- Audio in eLearning is often an afterthought. While many courses focus on glitzy visuals and interactive gamification, audio tends to get left behind.
- Well-recorded voice over audio is a critical component to increasing engagement in your eLearning program. The popularity of podcasts and audiobooks is steadily on the rise. This is a meaningful realization that learners crave quality audio content.
- Hearing is one of the core senses of human beings. With this knowledge, we must allocate sufficient resources to create an enjoyable and engaging listening experience. Just think of how fast you turn off a YouTube video if the audio doesn't meet your expectation.
- The first step in recording a good voiceover is to write a script. This helps keep your voiceover clean, on-subject, and most efficient for the learner. Once your script is cleaned up, you're ready to start recording.
- If you're serious about eLearning development, it's beneficial to use an external microphone. Try starting with a simple USB microphone and moving your way up to higher quality microphones as you gain experience. You'll also need a pair of headphones for the recording and editing process. This helps ensure your eLearning voiceover will sound clean and crisp on any device.

...I would underline this 3 or 4 times!

4. Keep everything on brand

- Have you requested brand guidelines from your university? How about their logos and color palette? If not, checking in with your university is the best place to start. They will often have a deck for you to use, or at least a few branded documents for you to base your eLearning program on.
- In general, it's best to avoid using a mix of too many colors. Stick with two to three of your client's top colors. And if you have a little flexibility, consider integrating colors that have been shown to improve learner engagement.
- Be thoughtful about color choices in every asset you build: images, infographics, videos, logos, headers, and beyond.
- Next, consider your font choices. These should also come directly from your client. If the client has no preference, make sure you use just 1-2 fonts that are simple and clean. Serif fonts are always a quality choice to make it easier for learners to read.

...I would underline this 3 or 4 times! Do this to avoid rework!

5. Add meaningful interactions

- Testing learners through recall is the most effective way to achieve long-term comprehension. Plus, it makes your eLearning program much more enjoyable!
- Meaningful interactions such as video embeds, quizzes, flip charts, or discussion questions are all simple ways to increase learner engagement.
- Another option is creating a game-based eLearning, also called gamification. When used properly, competitive games can be overwhelmingly powerful for boosting engagement and retention.
- To add meaningful interactions, you need to make sure your selected eLearning software has these features built-in. Software like Adobe Captivate, Articulate Storyline, and Articulate Rise are our preferred eLearning development tools. And all three have a lengthy list of interaction options to boost engagement in your eLearning.

very important, but with excellent narration and clean color concept you can add this later at any time!

6. Use humor or other elements of surprise

- Most online training programs have a reputation for boredom. As soon as online learners see a cheesy stock image of a man wearing a suit, they have already checked out. Disengaged. Over it.
- Try conducting a deeper analysis of your audience. What would make them pay attention? What would evoke emotion? What would make them laugh?
- While humor should never distract from the learning material, thoughtful injections of relevant comedy can be monumental in boosting engagement and enjoyment.
- Try gathering ideas from social media. Browse Facebook or trending videos on YouTube, and view what users are “sharing” and “liking” on these online platforms. While most content is used purely for entertainment purposes, they often provide deeper insight into the human psyche of interests and engagement.

**...very nice, and with excellent narration and clean color concept you can add this later at any time!
But it has to fit to your individual style!**

7. Keep your lessons short

- Trim the fat. Cut out the fluff.
- Learners in companies are often not personally choosing to take an eLearning course. It's most often assigned by a manager or an HR team member. This means that many employees will have limited time, and may have limited interest in the subject material.
- In case of this and to combat these barriers, make sure you keep your lessons short. A good rule of thumb is to keep self-paced eLearning courses to under 45-minutes. To do this, make sure to edit your text and voiceover scripts relentlessly.
- Break up modules into smaller, bite-sized chunks that are easier for learners to digest. Especially when it comes to video, aim to keep each video under 5-minutes.

In the university context my personal view is different. A lecture lasts 90 or 180 minutes and has often complex content. It does often make no sense to split this but you can interrupt this by exercises, by the hint to make a break, by a video etc. Anyway, students can stop the content at any time anyway!

**..90min lecture content remain 90min lecture content
and some topics should not be splitted! You are the expert!**

8. Use relevant analogies and examples

- Analogies are one of the most powerful tools in the world of learning. By using a relevant comparison of two items, learners are forced to analyze one item and transfer that analysis to the other item. To do this successfully, the learner must have a firm comprehensive grasp on both items.
- This simple comparison helps transform a complex idea into a relatable and memorable concept. Before you begin brainstorming analogies, it's best to ensure you fully understand your audience. As mentioned earlier, conduct a deeper analysis so you know your audience's culture, interests, likes, and dislikes. This will be immensely helpful to develop powerful analogies to enhance the learning experience.

9. Simplify, simplify, simplify

- Is your eLearning program simple enough? Not the content but the way how the course is operated by the user.
- And without the help of a human instructor that most in-person training courses have, simplicity in eLearning should be an ultimate priority.
- Ask a co-worker or friend to user-test your eLearning course before going live. Their feedback will help make adjustments and add clarity to boost learner engagement.

Dare to start simple with imported PPT slides with excellent voiceover. Work continuously on the optimization but keep operation simple, interesting, intuitive and sometimes surprising. Do not mix up simple content with simple operation. This might be different in a company context! We can expect from our students that they handle complex topics.

Simple operation does not mean simple content!

Reflection Questions after Unit 10

(Homework - workload target 60 minutes)

1. Apply Mayer's 12 Principles of Multimedia to the weaker of the 2 lectures you have chosen in preparation to this session.
2. Try to convert as many decorative and representational images to images which fulfil the 12 principles of Mayer. You may either do this directly in PPT or you decide to do this as handwritten on printouts of the chosen lecture
3. I am am sure you do know without detailed analysis which further lectures would deserve a revision. Create a hitlist of 5 lectures and a timeplan when you do the same exercise for these next lectures.
4. Review again the images of both lectures and consider the hints regarding animiations. Which to dos to you see for these lectures?

it's your turn!

Summary

1. Selecting media and technologies is a complex process, involving a very wide range of interacting variables.
2. The SECTIONS Model for Media Selection provides a neutral and well established model.
3. How does this help us if we want to realize a course?
 - My personal target at the beginning was not to do something perfect, which is based on latest research results.
 - My target was to survive and to be fast!
 - And exactly this is my recommendation to you!
4. Think of Mayer's 12 principles of Multimedia as 'guidelines' as you develop your digital learning experiences – learning videos, eLearning courses, and instructor-led PowerPoint presentations.
5. Based on 6 categories of graphics of Clark&Mayer, it is recommended that **decorative** and **representational** images are minimised, and instead focus on graphics that help the learner to understand the material presented, or organise the material in a useful way.
6. When starting your E-Learning activities do constantly review your content and structure with reference to the 9 guidelines to make E-Learning effective or to optimize it.
7. Dare to start simple but with excellent narration!

Preparation Questions for Unit 11 (Homework - workload target 60 minutes)

Prepare yourself for our lecture by creating for yourself an overview about existing Open Educational Resources and databases providing them

1. For example here you do find databases like this:
 - <https://oerworldmap.org/resource/?language=en&filter.about.additionalType.%40id=%5B%22https%3A%2F%2Foerworldmap.org%2Fassets%2Fjson%2Fpublications.json%23oer%22%5D>
 - <https://www.oercommons.org/>
2. You are you using already OER?
 1. If yes please describe briefly in PPT which resources you do use and how your experience is!
 2. Do you plan to use further OER? If yes please describe them as well briefly.
 3. If time allows you will be invited to present our experience regarding OER.
3. You have not used OER until now, please make yourself familiar with existing databases and
 1. choose at least 2 OER which you plan to use in the upcoming semester
 2. Please describe them briefly in PPT and explain how you plan to implement them in your teaching concept
 3. If time allows you will be invited to present our experience regarding OER

FOR NEXT SESSION

E-Learning to go

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